

α -Oximino- β -phenylhydrazones of Aroylacetarylamides and their Cyclisation into 1,2,3-Triazoles

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A number of α -oximino- β -phenylhydrazones of aroylacetarylamides have been synthesised. They were cyclised in thionyl chloride or acetic anhydride/sodium acetate to give 4-aryl-5-carboxy(arylamino)-2-phenyl-1,2,3-triazoles. Their elemental analysis, uv and ir spectra are recorded.

α -Oximinohydrazones have been shown to possess antiparasitic, fungicidal and bactericidal properties^{1,2}. They have also been shown to act as chelating agents for the quantitative estimation of transition metal ions³⁻⁵. Cyclisation of oximinohydrazones afforded *vic*-triazoles whose mechanism of formation has been proposed by Ruppert and Nilsson⁶. *vic*-Triazoles are shown to possess whitening property and pharmacological activity⁷⁻¹¹.

The present paper deals with preparation and characterisation of α -oximino- β -phenylhydrazones of aroylacetarylamides and their cyclised products 1,2,3-triazoles.

Experimental

Melting points of all the compounds are uncorrected. Nitrogen content was estimated by

micro Duma's method. Uv spectra were recorded on Beckman DK-2A and Specord UV-VIS spectrophotometers using ethanol as a solvent, and ir spectra (KBr) on a Card-Zeiss (Jena) UR-10 spectrophotometer.

α -Oximino- β -phenylhydrazinobenzoylacetylaniide^{1,2}
(1): α -Oximino benzoylacetylaniide (1.34 g) was dissolved in ethanol (~ 10 ml), and alcoholic solution of phenylhydrazine (0.55 g) was then added to it. After adding concentrated HCl (~ 1 ml) the mixture was stirred well and allowed to stand for 2-3 h with occasional stirring. The product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from aqueous ethanol. The phenylhydrazones of other α -oximino aroylacetarylamides were prepared in the same manner. The characteristics and analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND UV SPECTRAL DATA OF α -OXIMINO- β -PHENYLHYDRAZONES OF AROYLACETARYLAMIDES (1)

Sl. no.	R	R'	Mol. formula	Decomp. temp. °C	Colour	Yield %	Analysis N % : Found/(Calcd.)	λ_{max} (log ϵ_{max}) nm
1.	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	165	Orange yellow	90	14.91 (15.27)	325 (4.1), 245 (4.3)
2.	H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂	124	Orange yellow	60	14.41 (14.03)	300 (4.0), 247 (4.2)
3.	H	<i>m</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ 2:4	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂	160	Orange yellow	65	14.18 (14.51)	325-298* (4.2-4.1), 230 (4.2)
4.	NO ₂	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	122	Dark yellowish red	82	15.81 (16.02)	290-70* (5.6), 220-40* (5.7)
5.	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	100	Dark yellowish red	90	16.33 (16.02)	300-25* (4.8), 230-50*
6.	NO ₂	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	115	Dark yellowish red	93	16.56 (16.74)	260-70* (5.4), 230
7.	Cl	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	148	Deep yellow	70	14.56 (14.29)	333 (3.9), 250 (4.2)
8.	Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂	180	White	70	13.36 (13.08)	330-300* (4.3-4.1), 250 (4.3)
9.	Cl	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	160	Yellow	80	13.55 (13.27)	265 (4.1), 235 (4.3)
10.	Cl	<i>m</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ 2:4	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	185	Yellow	85	13.90 (13.34)	325 (4.4), 225 (4.3)

*Broad

5-Carboxyl(o-chloroanilino)-2,4-diphenyl-1,2,3-triazole (2): α -Oximino- β -phenylhydrazinobenzoylaceto-*o*-chloroanilide (0.6 g) was mixed with excess of freshly distilled thionyl chloride (~ 20 ml) and refluxed at 80–90° for 3 h. Excess of thionyl chloride was then distilled off at atmospheric pressure while the traces were removed by distillation in vacuum after adding benzene and petroleum ether successively. The semisolid residue was then repeatedly washed with petroleum ether. The product was then recovered in the solid form by adding diethyl ether. Ether was then allowed to evaporate and the fine powder obtained was dried at 50–60° and then kept in vacuum desiccator till the odour of thionyl chloride disappeared. The other triazoles were prepared in a similar manner from the corresponding oximinophenylhydrazone and are listed in Table 2.

The mechanism of the *vic*-triazole formation from the α -oximinophenylhydrazones in the presence of thionylchloride has been proposed in Scheme 1.

In α -oximinophenylhydrazones (Table 1) the uv absorption pattern was characterised by the presence of two bands around 215–250 and 280–340 nm. The uv absorption of phenylhydrazine in ethanol shows two maxima at 240 (log ϵ 3.8) and 284 nm¹⁴ (log ϵ 3.2). On comparing the data of phenylhydrazine with those given in Table 1 it is revealed that when the primary amino group of the phenylhydrazine is replaced by C=N group there is a bathochromic shift of the longer wavelength band (284 nm) of the order of 0–40 nm with increase in intensity (log ϵ = 0.8–2) while the 240 nm band remains almost unaffected (except in few cases) with increase in intensity (log ϵ = 0.3–1.9). These bands are

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND UV SPECTRAL DATA OF 1,2,3-TRIAZOLES (2)

Sl. no.	R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Colour	Yield %	Analysis N % : Found/(Calcd.)	λ_{max} (log ϵ_{max}) nm
1.	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₄ OCl	140	Reddish yellow	75	15.41 (14.97)	275 (5.9)
2.	H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂	86	White grey	73	15.38 (15.14)	260 (5.8)
3.	H	<i>m</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ 2:4	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₄ O	90	Orange yellow	70	15.40 (15.22)	280 (5.7)
4.	NO ₂	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₂ Cl	170	Yellow	75	16.59 (16.7)	265 (5.7)
5.	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₂ Cl	85	Brown	80	16.67 (16.7)	275 (5.6)
6.	NO ₂	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄	180	Lemon yellow	65	16.23 (16.87)	260 (5.9)
7.	Cl	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₄ OCl	190	Greyish white	60	15.30 (14.95)	270 (5.9)
8.	Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ OCl	200	Brownish white	75	13.14 (13.7)	260 (5.9)
9.	Cl	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	85	Red	60	14.1 (13.87)	265 (5.8)
10.	Cl	<i>m</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ 2:4	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₄ OCl	90	Reddish yellow	70	13.57 (13.96)	260 (5.8)

Results and Discussion

α -Oximino- β -phenylhydrazones of aroylacetarylamides have been assigned anti-configuration¹³ (1).

1

2

R = H, NO₂, Cl
R' = H, *p*-CH₃, *o*-Cl, *p*-Cl, *o*-OCH₃, 2,4-(CH₃)₂

attributed to the crossed conjugated system C₆H₅-NH-N=C-C-C-¹⁵. The uv spectral

data (Table 2) of 2,4,5-trisubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles show one intense band in the region 260–275 nm (log ϵ = 5.4–5.9), which is attributed to π - π^* transition for 1,2,3-triazole ring^{16,17}.

The ir spectra of α -oximino- β -phenylhydrazino-aroylacetarylamides exhibit bands in the region 3 100–3 400 cm⁻¹ which are attributed to free ν_{NH} of amide and ν_{OH} of oxime¹⁸. The bands at 1 590–1 600 and 935–965 cm⁻¹ are assigned to C=N and N-O stretchings, respectively¹⁹. The most important feature of the infrared spectra of *vic*-triazoles is the presence and location of the *vic*-triazole ring vibrations and ring breathing bands. The bands around 1 170 and 1 250 cm⁻¹ are attributed to *vic*-triazole ring vibration. The peaks around 1 140, 1 050, 1 000 and 900 cm⁻¹ are assigned to *vic*-triazole ring breathing and C-H in-plane deformations²⁰. The absence of N-O band in triazoles

Scheme 1

indicates the formation of triazole ring with the disappearance of OH of oximino group of oximino-hydrazone during the cyclodehydration reaction. The bands around 3450 and 3300 cm^{-1} are assigned

to NH of free and *trans*-associated secondary amide. The bands due to C=N and secondary amide (C=O) are located at their usual positions¹⁸.

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References

1. L. GIAMMANCO, *Ann. Chim.*, 1961, 51, 175.
2. V. S. MISRA and R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 763.
3. M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1968, 31, 32.
4. M. M. PATEL, M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 318.
5. M. M. PATEL, M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 773.
6. H. RUPPERT and W. NILSSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4262.
7. K. GUGLIEMO, S. HANS and I. J. FLETCHER, Ger. Pat. 2 213 839/1972 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, 78, 85945).
8. J. R. GEIGY, Fr. Pat. 2 097 448/1972 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1972, 77, 153927).
9. F. FRITZ, K. HANS and V. SALVATORE, Ger. Pat. 2 262 340/1973 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, 79, 147435).
10. W. DAVID, A. M. JELENSKY and LEE C. CHENEY, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 948.
11. M. OSAMU, F. SHUNZO and U. SUMIO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1972, 48, 2577.
12. L. KNORR, *Ann.*, 1887, 236, 80.
13. M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 841.
14. H. E. UNGNADE, "Organic Electronic Spectral Data", Interscience, New York, 1960, Vol. II, pp. 1946-52.
15. E. A. BRAUDE and E. R. H. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 498.
16. C. N. R. RAO, "Ultraviolet and Visible Spectroscopy", Butterworths, London, 1951, p. 52.
17. H. EL-KHADEM, A. M. KOLKAILA and M. H. MESHRAKI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 3531.
18. D. HADZI and J. JAN, *Rev. Roum. Chem.*, 1965, 10, 1183.
19. H. E. UNGNADE, G. FRITZ and L. W. KISSINGER, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 235.
20. C. N. R. RAO and R. VENKATRAGHAVAN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1964, 42, 43.